

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D6.2 QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the project organisation and documentation processes, in order to ensure that the partners follow well defined procedures and project management team is at all stages aware of the status of the project. The document also describes the measures for quality assurance of project results and documentation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action (part of the Grant Agreement)
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GA	General Assembly
IM	Innovation Manager
PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board
PMO	Project Management Office
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT

This document is the Quality Assurance Plan for the STADIEM Project.

The purpose of this document is to provide all project partners with a summary of the most important project procedures (project monitoring, reporting tools, financial management, internal communication structures, etc.). By defining the management and decisions structures and procedures in the project, it describes the quality assurance measures taken by the project.

1.2 QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN FOR THE PROJECT

The Quality Assurance Plan includes all procedures planned and set within the STADIEM consortium in order to assure high quality results for the project. This includes the management structure of STADIEM in detail, the applied quality assurance procedures and the project documentation.

For STADIEM, a flat management structure consisting of the project management with its assigned project office and Work Package (WP) leaders is applied. These management structures, their responsibilities and the decision rules are described in Section 2.

The quality assurance procedures applied within STADIEM include an internal review mechanism, project monitoring and standards & conventions on how to prepare documents. The internal review process has been defined for paper and software deliverables. Internal reviewers will be appointed at project meetings always at least six months ahead of the delivery date of the respective deliverable.

Project monitoring will be enabled by quarterly activity reports which are to be delivered by each partner to the WP leader on or before the three weeks after the end of the reporting period. A summarized report will be delivered to the coordinator by each WP leader at the latest on or before four weeks after the end of the reporting period, accompanied by financial statements and by the project management reports. Project management reports will be prepared with the help of WP leaders. The details are described in Section X.

In order to assure an efficient communication amongst a geographically dispersed consortium, the project management has put an internal communication infrastructure in place. This includes the setup of a central document store (Google Drive), a mailing list and a Slack workspace. The document store is the central repository for all project partners and is organized in areas. The WP folders are the main repository for documents (structured by tasks). The meetings folder covers agenda, presentations given at meetings and the minutes. Contracts and other official documents are collected in the “official documents” folder.

2 PROJECT ORGANISATION

2.1 OVERVIEW ON CONSORTIUM ORGANISATION

2.2 EUROPEAN COMMISSION

The Coordinator is the intermediary between the European Commission and the Consortium. At the European Commission, the responsible officer for STADIEM is Luis Eduardo Martinez Lafuente.

2.3 RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE MAIN PROJECT BODIES

2.3.1 General Assembly

The **General Assembly (GA)** is the operational body of the project. Chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC), it is formed by one representative of each partner. The GA will decide on matters related to the overall Work Plan. It will discuss - and make decisions on the basis of reports from the PMB and will indicate and guide actions that are deemed necessary for securing the uninterrupted progress of the project as a whole. The overall duties of the GA include: following up the project; releasing project results; managing potential problems and taking all contractual decisions. In the case that a major modification of the overall project will be required, the decision for such a change will be made after consultation with all the participating members.

The GA will meet twice per year. Additional meetings will be arranged if necessary, for urgent matters or if a majority of partners agree on it. Internal consensus among the project partners on managerial issues is vital to the project success. If a consortium member is not present or represented at a GA meeting without prior excuse, that partner is bound to honor the decisions taken and actions placed on him/her in absence. Whenever possible, all the decisions will be adopted by general consensus. Normally the GA will decide with a majority of 2/3 about the required modifications and changes due to events that arise during the course of the project.

2.3.2 Project Management Board

The **Project Management Board (PMB)** includes the PC, IM, and WP Leaders and is chaired by the PC. The PMB is responsible for setting business and technical strategy, resolving inter-partner issues and ensuring cross activity integration, overseeing the promotion of gender equality in the project, coordination at Consortium Level of technical activities, coordination of the overall legal, contractual, financial and administrative management. Moreover, PMB ensures that trials are conducted in consideration of ethical requirements and adhere to legal and ethical requirements, while overseeing the application of the ethical management strategy of the consortium. Some major decisions might be subject to further approval from the GA. The PMB meets at least once every three months (ordinary) and on any executive board member's demand (extraordinary). Bi-weekly status teleconferences are also planned.

2.3.2.1 Work package and task leaders

The Work Package Leader is responsible for

- Controlling and reporting of the progress of the work package;
- Collecting work reports from all parties and confirming the results of the parties (quarterly reports) in the corresponding work package;
- Evaluating possible actions and activities;
- Preparing, administrating and providing minutes as chairperson of work package meetings;
- Transmitting any documents and information connected with the work package between the parties concerned;
- Transmitting the project deliverables of the parties within the work package to the coordinator.
- Informing all concerned parties within the work package, other work package leaders of other affected work packages and the coordinator about delays if it is brought to his or her notice that a party is late in the submission of its planned results.

Similar to the Work Package Leader Task Leaders are responsible for the Work in their respective Tasks. The Task Leader is responsible for

- Task Leaders regularly report to the corresponding WP Leader.
- Any issues endangering the success of the Work Package or the project have to be reported immediately to the Project Coordinator (VRT) and discussed by telephone or E-mail.

2.3.3 Project Management Office

The **Project Management Office (PMO)** shall assist and facilitate the work of the PC for executing the decisions of the General Assembly as well as the day-to-day management of the project. The PMO will support partners in administrative matters; assist in the communication and collaboration setting-up, running and maintenance of the project, financial plan & monitoring, reporting, quality assurance and risk monitoring; organise and assist the running and following up of project meetings; follow schedules of reports and deliverables and support maintaining the schedule. The PMO will comprise of the Administration, Financial and Quality Managers. The PMO will be heavily involved in all the activities of WP6 – Project Coordination. **The PMO is provided by the coordinator (VRT).**

2.3.4 Innovation Hubs Board

The **Innovation Hubs Board (IHB)**: consists of representatives from the four STADIEM Innovation Hubs, with main responsibilities to a) the consistency, harmonisation and

convergence of the activities related to the Incubation Framework and Programme implementation throughout the four Hubs, b) the coordination of the planned joint kick-off and demo (closing) events of the third party projects, c) the exchange of lessons learnt and best practices during the implementation and assessment of the Programme, d) the proper design of the Open Calls' specifications in collaboration with the WP3 leader.

2.3.5 Advisory Board

The **Advisory Board (AB)** consists of selected experts in the field, from a diverse set of backgrounds and geographies, who (a) have expertise in a subset of the topics that the project is developing and (b) have direct access to a great range of the targeted user groups in the areas of the planned Open Calls and Incubation Programme of the project. The role of the AB includes a) contribute to the design of the project development and assessment framework, b) actively support the communication of the support funding scheme and opportunities, c) advise on the specifications related to the Open Calls, d) collaborate with the Innovation Hubs Board on issues related to the implementation of the Programme, e) inform the consortium about methodological, framework related, market or regulatory trends (among others) that are of relevance to the project work, f) increase the impact of the project by creating visibility of STADIEM in other geographic regions and in different sectors / groups of stakeholders, g) provide an external view of the project, in order to allow the project leadership to better position and articulate the public profile of the project.

2.4 MEETINGS AND COMMUNICATION

Internal information flow: Information flows both vertically and horizontally within the project structure. The vertical flow of information to/from the PMB comprises mainly the administrative issues, such as: (i) Periodic progress reporting of administrative information from all partners to the PC, and the distribution of the consolidated reports back from the Coordinator to all partners; (ii) Meetings of the GA for the contractual and administrative execution and monitoring of the project; (iii) Administration of advance payments and cost claims. The flow of information between the WPs is generally more appropriate to a less formal and horizontal process. Information will be exchanged between partners in the same WP through regular e-mail contact and/or slack. Details will be exchanged between partners working in different WPs, again by e-mail, but also during the Plenary meetings.

Meetings planning: The project will hold specific meetings for different purposes, both by meeting at a common location and via conference call. The PC in collaboration with the PMB will properly prepare the agenda of each meeting at least 14 days before the event. The PC will provide minutes and Action Points within 14 days of the end of the meeting. In addition to these project-level meetings, each WP Leader may organize WP meetings (teleconferences or face-to-face) to facilitate the correct progress of the work (discussion about technical and organizational items) at least on a monthly basis. Co-location with other meetings or events that the partners plan to attend will always be considered as the best option to optimize resources.

2.5 CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Problems have to be reported as early as possible to the Project Coordination in order to immediately define and apply mechanisms for remedial actions (if necessary) within the respective boards. For more information – please have a look on the documents “Description of Action” and “Consortium Agreement” available on the document store.

Conflicts between project partners and/or team members have a major influence on the overall success of the project. Therefore it is the responsibility of the Project Coordination to deal immediately with these conflicts in order to avoid major damage to the project.

There are many procedures mentioned in the Consortium Agreement for avoiding any conflicts, however in case of any conflict, the General Assembly will act as the highest conflict resolution level within the project. The members of the General Assembly will be in charge of analysing any problems and providing proposals for a solution in an amicable way. Any Consortium member may, however, contact the Project Coordination or the respective boards directly if they identify an actual or potential conflict. The Coordinator will immediately attempt to resolve this by discussion or by calling an ad hoc meeting. If conflicts cannot be solved in this way, voting on the issue will be necessary.

If a conflict cannot be resolved at one level, the next board up the management chain will be involved, which will decide using the voting structures and procedures set out in the Consortium Agreement. In most cases, each member has one vote and simple majority decisions will be taken. Where partners are failing to meet their obligations, where serious financial measures need to be taken or partners may be excluded from the project, are treated in a different way and require two-thirds majorities of all members of the General Assembly with a casting vote by the Coordinator in case of a tie.

3 CONTRACTUAL FRAMEWORK

The contractual framework of STADIEM will consist mainly of two core contracts which are mandatory for EC funded projects within Horizon 2020: the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. It will be complemented by a set of contracts related to the financial support to third parties through the STADIEM open calls.

3.1 GRANT AGREEMENT

The basis for all EC funded projects is the signed project Grant Agreement which regulates the relationship between the European Commission and the Project Consortium.

The European Commission signed the Grant Agreement with the Project Coordinator. All other project partners signed Accession Forms to the contract in order to be integrated within the project. The Grant Agreement contains all specific project details like project start date, project duration, budget, project results etc.

The Grant Agreement consists of the following parts:

- Terms and Conditions
- Annex 1 Description of the action
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action
- 2a Additional information on the estimated budget
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Model for the certificate on the financial statements
- Annex 6 Model for the certificate on the methodology

You can find the Grant Agreement including annexes on the project document store.

3.2 CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT

The Consortium Agreement is mandatory for EC projects. It regulates the cooperation within the project consortium and mainly contains the following topics:

- Legal name, address and authorised people to sign the contract of all partners
- Preamble
- Subject of the contract (title of project)
- Organisational provisions (project boards and their responsibilities, management, voting procedures, ...)
- Financial provisions (financing plan, modification procedures, auditing of costs, payments, ...)
- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and commercial provisions (confidentiality, ownership of results, legal protection of rights, exploitation of results, background know-how, ...)
- Dissemination of knowledge (publications, trade-shows etc.)

- Legal provisions (legal form of the cooperation, duration of the agreement, applicable law, settlement of disputes, ...)

During the project the Consortium Agreement may “evolve” and be changed by agreement of all partners, e.g. to take into account changes in the partner structure, additional rules for exploitation or protection of generated knowledge.

The Consortium Agreement can be found on the project document store.

4 OBJECTIVES AND KPI'S

The overall ambition of STADIEM is to boost the opportunities and success of media startups by developing and growing in close cooperation with corporate and venture partners, securing a sustainable growth to success.

To track the successful achievement of this ambition, STADIEM has set out concrete strategic objectives with KPI's, a set of impact assessment KPI's and a list of KPI's related to dissemination and communication. Details on the KPI's are found in Annex I Part B of the Grant Agreement. They will be however briefly listed in the sections below.

4.1 STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

O1. Set up a cross-border community of ecosystems that brings together 4 innovation hubs focused on media acceleration and achieve seamless collaboration between the hubs and their pool of emerging tech-innovators by offering an intensive incubation program of selected startups/ scaleups.

Expected outcomes (quantitative):

- Establishment of the STADIEM ecosystem with its ecosystem map. The ecosystem map will contain an inventory of stakeholders in the community and their roles.
- A list of opportunities for stakeholders in the ecosystem to collaborate with startups
- A validated community building strategy

Furthermore, an ecosystem engagement strategy is expected to lead to engaged startups in the programme. The target is to engage over 300 startups willing to join the programme across the 2 foreseen open calls, out of which at least 80 will be selected to participate in the first stage of the programme. These targets are linked with the open call strategy in O4.

O2. Develop a cross-border European market-driven mediatech support framework and toolset

Expected outcomes:

STADIEM will deliver a coherent **startup incubation and acceleration framework**, together with a set of tools through which the progress of startups in the programme can be monitored. The framework will be revised throughout the project incorporating learnings from the first open call.

O3. To offer the framework to young innovating companies through a dedicated and coherent startup support programme, offered through 2 open calls.

Expected outcomes:

(Qualitative)

- A validated cross-border scaleup programme
- Qualitative assessment by start-ups of available services and mentoring
- Feedback of founders on founder 2 founder networking
- Survey of investors on startup maturity and progress
- Feedback from startups on mentoring and coaching activities

(Quantitative)

- At least 10 coaches per hub involved in the coaching and mentoring activities

- A target of at least 5 coaching sessions per selected startup organized during the project, and more for startups which proceed further in the programme.
- At least 4 client introductions per selected startup organized during the project
- At least 2 investor introductions per selected startup organized during the project

O4. To attract and engage at least 300 and to select at least 80 tech innovators with emerging technology driven concepts to participate in the collaborative and progressive 4-stage incubation programme aiming to support the development and market uptake of the most impactful and ambitious ones.

Expected outcomes:

- Receive a total of at least 300 applications (across 2 open calls) to select at least 80 to enter the Match phase of STADIEM programme.
- Support at least 32 projects through the Develop, at least 24 at the Integration and at least 8 at the Pilot phases
- Invest 3.86 million in tech-innovators
- Be able to generate potential investments for STADIEM third-parties above €15m
- Send at least 80 startups to all four European hubs on an Inspiration and Market tour
- To allocate at least 315 hours to mentor and support tech innovators (per hub)
- Results of each programme stage will be presented in 2 ecosystem demo events and as part of STADIEM participation in at least 10 relevant industry events.

O5. Create synergies with relevant activities in Europe and worldwide towards a sustainable community, to foster STADIEM awareness, and to offer improved services to the startups and scaleups within the network.

Expected outcomes:

- Receive a total of at least 300 applications (across 2 open calls) to select at least 80 to enter the Match phase of STADIEM programme.
- Support at least 32 projects through the Develop, at least 24 at the Integration and at least 8 at the Pilot phases
- Invest 3.86 million in tech-innovators
- Be able to generate potential investments for STADIEM third-parties above €15m
- Send at least 80 startups to all four European hubs on an Inspiration and Market tour
- To allocate at least 315 hours to mentor and support tech innovators (per hub)
- Results of each programme stage will be presented in 2 ecosystem demo events and as part of STADIEM participation in at least 10 relevant industry events.

O5. Create synergies with relevant activities in Europe and worldwide towards a sustainable community, to foster STADIEM awareness, and to offer improved services to the startups and scaleups within the network.

Expected outcomes:

- STADIEM will keep track of the links between external initiatives. The objective is to connect at least 10 relevant initiatives. and to participate in at least 10 event collaborations with other initiatives

O6. To ensure post-project sustainability and growth of the STADIEM ecosystem/incubator.

Expected outcomes:

- At least one non-media sector engaged to explore STADIEM incubator collaboration opportunities

- Identification and definition of 2-5 concrete funding opportunities for post-project sustainable operation
- +8x% percentage of STADIEM budget will be dedicated to support emerging tech innovators (7x% through direct funding/ sub-grants and 1x% through services provided by the partners)
- Business model and sustainability plan

4.2 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

To realize the ambition of the STADIEM project and yield high-level impact to the goals and objectives of the call, contribute to Europe's media ecosystems, and boost the project's beneficiaries and stakeholders, STADIEM will implement a comprehensive, multi-stage impact monitoring and assessment strategy that will be utilized to steer and give action-driven feedback to all stages of the project's execution.

STADIEM proposes a three-level impact strategy closely monitoring the project's cycle in a whole and holistic manner:

1. Ecosystem impact to the European media sector and the call's objectives; STADIEM network, Hubs, Stakeholders, Startups, and Beneficiaries
2. STADIEM Framework / Program impact to Open calls, Framework deployment, Pilots, and Multidimensional stakeholder feedback to the framework progress & deployment
3. Dissemination impact to project's visibility and media coverage; social media; community development; and events & presentations

The impact will be assessed through a set of KPI's, which can be found in Table 4 of Annex I Part B of the STADIEM Grant Agreement.

4.3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

STADIEM activities and plan will include offline and online communications, digital presence, participation to and organization of events, interaction with the other research and innovation projects in the domain, and liaisons with relevant stakeholders.

An overall impact creation, communication and dissemination strategy, together with the corresponding KPI's can be found in Section 2.2.1 of Annex I Part B of the STADIEM Grant Agreement.

5 PROJECT DOCUMENTATION

Each partner has to document the project progress during the duration of the project. This documentation will be the basis on which all efforts, payments, audits and so on will be checked and verified.

5.1 STADIEM TEMPLATES

The communications coordinator has devised a set of templates for project reports, presentations and communications. All partners are expected to use the dedicated templates for such purposes. At the time of writing this QA Plan, the following templates are available for the partners on the document repository:

- STADIEM Deliverable template, to be used for all official STADIEM deliverables
- STADIEM Presentation template, to be used for all internal and external presentations.

The templates come with a dedicated font (Encode Sans) that should be installed to use the correct layout. The font is also available in the document repository.

Further templates might be designed whenever needed. Partners are expected to follow all current and future available templates.

Questions and feedback on the templates should be sent to the communications coordinator Martel Innovate.

5.2 QUARTERLY REPORTING OF PROJECT PROGRESS

The project progress will need to be reported by all partners on a three-monthly basis. For this purpose an Excel reporting sheet has been prepared and will be made available for partners.

The goals of the three-monthly status report are:

- ➔ documentation of project progress
- ➔ to discover deviations at an early stage and
- ➔ to start remedial actions (if necessary) as soon as possible.

The partners enter their progress works into the reporting sheet within 3 weeks after the end of each quarter. The work package leaders will then approve the submitted reports within one week. Each work package leader provides a summary of the works done in his work package to the project co-ordinator.

5.3 PERIODIC REPORTS

A Periodic Report is required at the end of each reporting period (M18, M36) as defined in the Grant Agreement. The Periodic Report contains the report on overall project progress as well as on financial statements (see Section 6.3.1). The Project Coordinator will merge the information provided by the partners in reporting tool to one report. WP Leaders are asked to consolidate the documentation of their work package. The consolidated report is submitted to the European Commission.

5.4 INTERMEDIATE MANAGEMENT REPORTS

In addition to the reports at the end of the reporting period, intermediate management reports are delivered in M8 (D6.4), M14 (D6.5) and M26 (D6.6) and M32 (D6.7). The procedure is the same as for other management reports.

5.5 TIME SHEETS

Please note that all consortium partners have to keep time sheets (contractually obligatory according to the Grant Agreement) for each project employee on a monthly basis. These time sheets are necessary to demonstrate your working hours in the case the European Commission will have the project efforts checked by independent auditors. You may use your own institution's timesheets provided they are giving sufficient information.

5.6 DELIVERABLES

Deliverables (reports, prototypes, etc.) are evidences of the project's performance and enable the Coordinator and the Commission to monitor the project.

- The responsible partner, i.e. Lead Beneficiary, compiles the deliverable with the support of the other partners assigned to this specific task.
- Internal Review: An internal review procedure for deliverables will be established according to the Quality Assurance for Deliverables (see 5.6.2) in order to improve the quality of each deliverable.
- The responsible partner forwards the deliverable and the related deliverable review report to the Project Coordinator (leaving at least one working day for formal checks) who will transmit the Deliverable to the Commission.

Please note that a deliverable template has to be used for all deliverables created within the project. You can find the template document on the project document store.

5.6.1 List of Official Deliverables

Official Deliverables that will be made available to the EC are listed in the DoA in WT2. The list is also included below.

5.6.2 Quality Assurance for Deliverables

The Quality Assurance Plan foresees the following procedure to assure the quality for deliverables:

- One month before the deadline: Responsible partner shares the ToC of the deliverable with the contributing partners and the WP leader.
- Two weeks before deadline: Responsible partner sends deliverable in final draft to the internal reviewer
- One week before deadline: Internal reviewer sends back Review Report to responsible partner
- Deadline: Responsible partner send final version deliverable together with Review Report (including author's response) to the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator submits the deliverable to the EC.

This means that the final draft of the deliverable has to be sent to the internal reviewer at least two weeks before the deadline in order to allow enough time to comment and make adjustments.

5.6.3 Deliverable Reviewers

Deliverable reviewers are assigned during project meetings. The list of deliverables together with the responsible internal reviewer will be kept up-to-date in a project management document on the document store. The internal reviewers for the first upcoming deliverables are also listed in the table below. It will be further completed during the regular meetings of STADIEM.

WP	Nr.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination level	Due date	Internal review
6	D6.1	Internal communication platform	VRT	Report	Confidential	M01	/
1	D1.1	Community Building Strategy	VRT	Report	Public	M03	MCB
5	D5.1	STADIEM website	Martel	Report	Public	M03	VRT
6	D6.2	Quality assurance plan	VRT	Report	Public	M03	Martel
3	D3.1	Open call documents KIT and third-party financing rules v1	F6S	Report	Public	M04	ST
5	D5.2	Outreach and impact creation strategy and plan	Martel	Report	Public	M04	VRT
2	D2.1	Cross border innovation, business development and scaling framework for European media sector startups	ST	Report	Confidential	M05	NMA
2	D2.2	Analysis and implementation of effective startup program management toolkit for the European media sector	MCB	Report	Confidential	M05	EA (Heikki)

1	D1.2	Community map and database v1	VRT	Report	Confidential	M06	
6	D6.7	Data Management Plan	VRT	ORDP	Confidential	M06	
7	D7.1	H - requirement No. 1	VRT	Ethics	Confidential	M06	
6	D6.3	Half year interim project and innovation management report until M6	VRT	Report	Confidential	M07	
5	D5.3	Impact methodological framework	ST	Report	Public	M08	
3	D3.3	Open Call 1 report	F6S	Report	Confidential	M09	
3	D3.5	Analytics on the submitted proposals open call 1	F6S	Report	Public	M09	
1	D1.5	Community Building activity report v1	VRT	Report	Public	M12	
6	D6.4	Half year interim project and innovation management report until M12	VRT	Report	Confidential	M13	
2	D2.3	A comprehensive startup incubation framework and toolkit for the European media sector startup industry v1	ST	Report	Public	M15	
3	D3.2	Open call documents KIT and third-party financing rules v1	F6S	Report	Public	M15	
4	D4.1	Match and Develop phases report - the 1st cycle	MCB	Report	Public	M17	
5	D5.4	Impact creation and assessment report v1	ST	Report	Public	M18	

5	D5.6	Market analysis, exploitation and sustainability v1	NMA	Report	Confidential	M18	
5	D5.8	Outreach and impact creation activities report v1	Martel	Report	Public	M18	
1	D1.3	Community map and database v2	VRT	Report	Confidential	M20	
3	D3.4	Open call 2 report	F6S	Report	Confidential	M20	
3	D3.6	Analytics on the submitted proposals open call 2	F6S	Report	Public	M20	
4	D4.2	Integration, piloting phases and assessment report - the 1st cycle	NMA	Report	Public	M23	
1	D1.6	Community Building activity report v2	VRT	Report	Public	M24	
6	D6.5	Half year interim project and innovation management report until M24	VRT	Report	Confidential	M25	
4	D4.3	Match and Develop phases report - the 2nd cycle	VRT	Report	Public	M28	
6	D6.6	Half year interim project and innovation management report until M30	VRT	Report	Confidential	M31	
4	D4.4	Integration, piloting phases and assessment report - the 2nd cycle	ST	Report	Public	M34	
2	D2.4	A comprehensive startup incubation framework and toolkit for the European media	ST	Report	Public	M35	

		sector startup industry v2					
1	D1.4	Community map and database v3	VRT	Report	Confidential	M36	
1	D1.7	Community Building activity report v3	VRT	Report	Public	M36	
5	D5.5	Impact creation and assessment report v2	ST	Report	Public	M36	
5	D5.7	Market analysis, exploitation and sustainability v2	NMA	Report	Confidential	M36	
5	D5.9	Outreach and impact creation activities report v2	Martel	Report	Public	M36	

5.6.4 Issues to be checked by Internal Reviewer

The internal reviewer has to check the quality of the deliverable concerning the issues listed below and compiles a Review Report. A template for the Review Report can be found on the document store.

- Ensure conformance of Deliverable to the Description of Action
- Furthermore check document for
 - clear and concise structure
 - executive summary
 - introduction / related documents
- Check for references: text copied without reference?
- Formal presentation: document template used? etc.
- Recommend corrective actions if necessary

5.7 EC REVIEWS

EC reviews will be organised to present the project results in regular periods (in most cases: annually) to the European Commission and their independent experts. This enables the Commission to monitor the project and to ensure that the contractual obligations are fulfilled. Additionally future project plans are discussed and agreed within such a meeting.

Reviews are scheduled after M12, M24 and M36, with the tentative location Brussels. Reviews take place within 60 days of the end of the corresponding period.

5.8 EXTERNAL PUBLICATIONS INCL. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The Coordinator and all partners have to be informed on project related publications well in advance (see also the DoA and the CA for details). External publications should be joint publications between project partners, whenever possible. References to published articles will be stored on the project's public web page <https://www.stadiem.eu>. If possible, PDF versions of publications should also be made available, but complying to the publisher's copyright rules.

The Intellectual Property rights (especially in connection with planned patents) as included in the Consortium Agreement have to be respected.

In any publication, the following notice must be included:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957321.

or

This [insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957321.

When possible, the EU flag must be used, in a size similar to other logos present.

Whenever possible/applicable, the following disclaimer should be included:

The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

In case of doubt, contact the STADIEM Communication and Dissemination responsible partner Martel Innovate.

6 FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

6.1 PAYMENTS BY THE COMMISSION

The contract specifies a maximum EC contribution to the project.

Payments are made to the Project Coordinator on behalf of the consortium. The Project Coordinator is responsible for receiving and ensuring the distribution of the community financial contribution. The allocation of the payments to the partners has to be decided by the consortium (consortium agreement).

Whenever changes regarding the bank account information occur on the partner's side the Project Coordinator has to be informed immediately.

By a system of periodic advance payments (pre-financing) a permanent positive cash flow is guaranteed, giving great financial certainty to the consortium. Details on the distribution of the prefinancing are included in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

6.2 FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES

STADIEM includes financial support to third parties (FSTP) through dedicated open calls to take place during the execution of the project. The PC is responsible for the correct management of the funds dedicated to the FSTP. A dedicated contractual framework will be set up during the project, through Task 3.3.

6.3 FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND CERTIFICATE ON THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS CFS

6.3.1 Financial Statements

Financial statements cover each partner's cost claim for the previous project period. After the end of the reporting period the participants enter their financial statements, the explanation of the use of the resources and upload the certificate on the financial statement (if required) into NEF via the EC Research Participant Portal.

The Project coordinator submits the entries from all partners to the Commission via NEF (together with the Project Management Report).

6.3.2 Certificate on the Financial Statements CFS

If the cumulative funding is less than 325.000€, no certificate is required. Otherwise, partners need to include a CFS in their financial report.

The auditor must be an independent, external and qualified to national regulations. He certifies that costs incurred during period meet the conditions required by the contract; should expressly state amounts verified

Make early contact with your external auditor and establish with him how to submit cost claims/certificates 45 days after end of period.

The coordinator has to submit all final reports and financial statements from all participants (including signed original financial statements) within 60 days after end of each period to EC, which means the financial statement and the audit certificate (if required) of all partners should be with the coordinator **at least 2 weeks before the submission to EC**.

Costs of certificates are an eligible cost.

7 RISK MANAGEMENT

A crucial task for the management of an ambitious project such as STADIEM is to ensure the proper balance and coordination between the different project activities as well as between partners with different areas of expertise, especially taking into account the highly expected numbers of the 3rd parties involved / engaged and the ambition of the project Incubation Programme. The management must be able to address and harmonize different aspects emerging from the various planned activities. To this end, risk management is a high priority and will be organized as follows:

1. Risk Identification: during the initial start-up of the project, a risk assessment will be conducted to identify risks associated with both the business and technical aspect of the research. Risks will be assessed for their impact on the project and the probability of the risk materializing.
2. Risk analysis: evaluating the attributes of a risk implies establishing values for probability (the likelihood the risk will occur) and the impact that their occurrence might have on the planned work (in terms of significance for the specific project objectives).
3. Risk response: defining actions to be performed if and when a specific risk occurs. The key idea is to identify who owns the risk – who is responsible for this within the consortium or outside – and what can/should be done to minimize its impact.
4. Risk monitoring: this ongoing task keeps track of the risks and evaluates the effectiveness of the response actions. Monitoring may also provide a basis for developing additional response actions and identifying new risks.

The PMB will supervise this process and enforce risk mitigation plans as appropriate to reduce the impact and likelihood of the risks occurring. This integrated approach to risk management will enable effective control of the business, intellectual property, technology, people, management, environment and other implementation risks that may arise. Unresolved issues or conflicts impacting the project will be handled by the PMB.

The following table contains the major risks currently identified for the execution of the project.

Description of risk	WP(s)	Impact / Prob	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Management risks			
Complexity in management	WP6	Med. / Low /	Most of the partners have collaborated in the past under other projects bringing excellent results. Besides, VRT, have great experience in Coordinating successfully completed or in progress projects with large Consortiums.
Partner leaving the consortium	WP6, PMB	Med. / Low	From an administrative and financial point of view, the loss of a partner will be regulated by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement that will define the terms under which a partner will be allowed to leave and ensure that resources (budget) will be available to finalize the work. In the case that a partner goes bankrupt, the Guarantee Fund

			will provide the necessary replacement budget. The leaving of a partner can have impacts on the consortium profile in three main aspects: skills, weakening of the industrial profile and loss of critical infrastructure. In a first step, we would consider continuing the work with the remaining partners, identifying equivalent skills or industrial profiles among other partners and sharing out the outstanding duties between the remaining partners. In the case that skills or industrial profiles turn out to be missing among the remaining partners, assistance will be sought by introducing a new partner.
Partner is underperforming	WP6, PMB	Low / Med.	Quarterly reporting and continuous monitoring by the PMB will avoid undiscovered underperforming. In any such case the mitigation plan includes reactivating the partners and in the worst case remove / replace as necessary.
Shortage of resources	WP6, PMB	Med. / Low	If the requirements analysis and design phase of the project reveals that the dedicated resources and time-schedule are not compliant with the wideness of the topic, a scope reduction might be applied, e.g. additional assumptions introduced to limit the complexity. Nevertheless, a full plan of development and validation based upon the subset will be run. It is coherent with IP scheme, which supports progress towards long-term goals.
Respecting the planning and meeting the deadlines	WP6	Low / Med.	The risk is reduced by partners expertise (technical skills and management experience) that will permit anticipating planning drifts, and by carefully planned work package timing and dependencies. Delays will be immediately reported to the technical manager who will perform proper actions to reduce the delay.
Technical implementation risks			
Startups unable to find corporate partners	WP4	Med. / Low	The risk is reduced by involving companies that the hubs know well, and therefore able to brief and prepare the ground before the Matching phase starts. Our 4 stage strategy is also based on the assumption that some startups will indeed not be able to find a corporate partner and that the group of startups will be reduced as we proceed through the phases
Failure in the pilot phase	WP4	Med. / Low	There are always risks associated with the piloting of services, which can be down to the integration of the service to be piloted, the service itself, or the performance of the two parties involved. We have reduced the risk by ensuring that the startups secure a corporate partner already in the initial stages, and that the communication and preparation for the pilot can be ongoing all the way through the project. And

			most of all, that we have set aside 2 months and a significant budget for the integration phase prior to the pilot.
No smooth flow of the startup tour/startup is unable to continue the tour /deadlines of the tour can't be kept	WP4	Med. / Med.	The startup tour is ambitious, so a good succession by each of the hubs is needed. Continuous follow-up of the startups by all of the partners will make sure this risk is avoided to a maximum and that targeted adjustments are taken care of.
Limited reactions to the open call	WP3	Med/high	All of the partners have an extended startup network. However, as the startup tours are ambitious, it might be that there are not enough applications to join the program. In that case, extra communication efforts will be worked out by the hub member(s).
Experts don't deliver	WP4	Low/Med	The risk is reduced, because an official and a reserve list can be created. If needed and thus in case of a lack of presence and deliverance by the experts new experts from the reserve list can be contacted to ensure follow-up.
Hub board member(s) quit	all	Med / Low	Hub board members are continuously aware of all project evolutions. The risk that one drops out is limited, however this might cause difficulties as a new board member doesn't know the project that well. This can be solved by making sure this person gets the right insights fast.
Failure of the community building strategy	WP1	Med / Low	Every single partner in STADIEM has a proven track record in community building. This is not only true for the hubs, but also for the other partners Martel, EBU and F6S. If the chosen community building appears to fail during the project, STADIEM will count on the ample experience and expertise present in the consortium to cope with this challenge and to identify alternative strategies.
Lack of identified opportunities for startups	WP1	Med / Low	All 4 hubs have been spotting opportunities for startups during their programmes in the incubators or accelerators. If, for any reason, 1 of the hubs fails to find sufficient opportunities for collaboration, other hubs can jump in to ensure STADIEM can offer sufficient opportunities for startups. If necessary, STADIEM will also reach out to other networks such as the Sandbox Hub in search for even more opportunities.
Failure to create high impact pan-European	WP2	Med / Med	The risk is reduced by the wide experience of consortium members of running dedicated startup support and development programs which effective methodologies, practices and lessons learned are combined and

<p>framework meeting the project ambitions</p>			<p>synchronized to create the STADIEM framework. Also, activities to harmonize and synchronize findings from dedicated startup support programs are discussed between the partners prior to the launch of the project. Extensive risk mitigation activities are being applied throughout the project through impact assessment methods to measure the effectiveness and impact the curriculum, 3rd party stakeholder feedback, and frequent communication between the project partners a to implement changes to the framework according to the project goals. Preliminary activities to Additionally, wider corrections are planned to be implemented during the lessons learned from the first incubation period to ensure the effectiveness of the project during the second open call and following incubation period.</p>
<p>Delivery and assessment tools are not fully implemented and utilized</p>	<p>WP2</p>	<p>Med / Low</p>	<p>Effective framework delivery and assessment tools are central to the success o the STADIEM project. The risk is mitigated by performing an extensive analysis and consultation between the project partners and 3rd party stakeholders to develop and implement effective and frequently utilized toolkit. Workshops and briefings are held throughout the project to ensure all project members, beneficiaries and other stakeholders are correctly and frequently utilizing the toolkit to the full capacity needed by the project.</p>

